

Small-sized bassoons from the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries under investigation

By Donna Agrell and Áurea Domínguez

Introduction

A new research project, "*Fagottini* and *tenoroons* - small, forgotten giants: Exploring the eighteenth- and nineteenth-century history, repertoire and usage of small-scale bassoons in performance and pedagogy" began its work at the Schola Cantorum Basiliensis in October 2017. Funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation, the two-year pilot project is focusing on the documentation of surviving eighteenth- and nineteenth-century instruments and compiling a repertoire list for small-scale bassoons.¹ Led by Prof. Dr. Thomas Drescher, director of the Schola Cantorum Basiliensis, the fagottino project team further consists of five historical bassoon performers and teachers: Prof. Dr. Donna Agrell, SCB and Royal Conservatoire The Hague, Dr. Áurea Domínguez, Giovanni Battista Graziadio, Zoë Matthews, and Letizia Viola.

The tasks of two main work groups in this phase are:

- Uncovering, re-classifying and listing repertoire for small bassoons, as well as researching historical performance issues and pedagogical traditions of these instruments; and
- Focusing on the collection and evaluation of organological data, aiming to produce a first instrument catalogue of fagottini and tenoroons from the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries.

Overshadowed instruments

Almost everyone has seen these small-scale instruments, found in the exhibitions of most major musical instrument museums, standing in the shadow of their larger counterparts. Because they are generally viewed as some kind of curiosity or toy, sparse explanations for their construction or descriptions of their use have been given. James B. Kopp dedicated a

¹ URLs: <https://www.fhnw.ch/de/forschung.../fagottini-und-tenoroons>; and <http://p3.snf.ch/project-173363>
The project's website is scheduled to "go live" shortly at: www:historical-bassoon.ch

whole chapter on the subject of small bassoons in *The Bassoon* (2012), naming makers and possible performance works, while Klaus Hubmann (2011) proposed a theory about their functions.² But on the whole, relatively little research has been done on the subject and these small historical bassoons have yet to take a place in performance and pedagogy.

Small-scale bassoons would have continued to go unnoticed if for the fact that there are just too many of them to plausibly ignore today; furthermore, it is evident that models were constructed by the most reputable eighteenth- and nineteenth-century woodwind makers and workshops throughout Europe, such as Denner, Grenser, Adler, and Savary. We have compiled a list of over 100 surviving small-sized bassoons in our instrument catalogue over the last year and will surely discover more.³

Only a half-dozen or so works scored for fagottino have been located, which is peculiarly disproportion to the number of surviving instruments. The most important questions of what music they were used for, by whom, and where, have not yet been fully answered. Kopp and Hubmann have pointed out that various well-known works such as Mozart's *Sonate für Fagott und Violoncello*, KV 292 and Beethoven's *Trio für Klavier, Flöte und Fagott*, WoO 37, were possibly composed with a small-sized bassoon in mind, and proposed that a re-examination of the bassoon repertoire might also be in order.⁴

Confusion of terminology

Today if one makes an online search for the term “fagottini”, the results number over 856,000 and mostly all are related to recipes containing an Italian pasta and defined by Wikipedia as: “fagot'ti:ni (Italian: little bundles) is a form of pasta. They are typically pasta shapes filled with vegetables, typically steamed carrots and green beans”. In musical circles, “fagottino” is the commonly-known name used for the small modern bassoons, pitched a fourth or fifth higher than the full-sized instrument.

Terminology describing small-scale bassoons in historical sources from the nineteenth century is confusing and contradictory, also with regional differences: In 1840, Josef

² James B. Kopp, *The Bassoon* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2012), Chapter 11, 222–28.^[1]
 Klaus Hubmann, ‘Hoch gestimmte Fagotte (Tenorfagotte) in der Musik vom späten 16. bis zum späten 18. Jahrhundert’, in: Christian Ahrens and Gregor Klinke (ed.), *Flöte, Oboe, Klarinette und Fagott: Holzbalsinstrumente bis zum Ende des 18. Jahrhunderts* (Tage Alter Musik in Herne 2008; München–Salzburg: Katzbichler, 2011), 78–84.

³ Available soon at: www.historical-bassoon.ch

⁴ Kopp (2012), 225. Hubmann (2011), 78–84.

Fahrbach wrote about the various sizes in the bassoon family in his *Neueste Wiener Fagottschule, Op 17*, mentioning a full-size bassoon (“gewöhnliches Fagott”) and a tenor bassoon (“Tenor-Fagott”) playing a fifth higher than the first, adding that this is called “fagottino” in Italian. He also notes that a “Quart-Fagott” is pitched a fourth *lower* than the full-sized bassoon (figure 1).⁵

Von den verschiedenen Arten Fagotte.

Es gibt in Beziehung auf die Grösse und Stimmung mehrere Arten Fagotte. 1^{te} Die gewöhnliche Fagott, dessen Töne den Tönen des *Violoncells* entsprechen und welchen wir im vorliegenden Werke abhandeln; 2^{te} der *Tenor-Fagott*, *ital. Fagottino* genannt, dessen Töne, gemäss der engeren *Mensur*, um eine *Quinte* höher klingen; 3^{te} der *Quart-Fagott*, welcher um eine *Quarte* tiefer, und 4^{te} der *Contra-Fagott*, welcher um eine *Octave* tiefer klingt, als der gewöhnliche Fagott. In Hinsicht der Spielart sind alle diese Arten der Fagotte einander ganz gleich, so, dass der Unterschied nur im Klange liegt. Der *Tenor-Fagott* wird nur für das *Solo* und gleich dem *Quart-Fagotte*, selten mehr gebraucht. Der *Contra-Fagott* jedoch ist nach dem gewöhnlichen

Fig. 1: Josef Fahrbach, *Neueste Wiener Fagottschule, Op 17* (1840)

Descriptions of the different-sized instruments are also offered in Carl Almenröder’s method from around the same time (figure 2). He depicts a smaller instrument as being pitched a fourth, and not a fifth higher than the full-sized one.

Fig. 2: Carl Almenröder, *Vollständige theoretisch praktische Fagottschule* (1843)

⁵ Josef Fahrbach, *Neueste Wiener Fagottschule, Op 17* (Vienna: Diabelli n.d. [1840]), 15. The larger “Quart-Fagott” is a very rare instrument, of which only several exist.

Almenräder also discusses terminology used for *larger* bassoons, pointing out that the “Quart-Fagott” cited in Zedler’s *Universal Lexicon* from the eighteenth century is actually a “Quint-Fagott”, a fifth lower than the full-scale bassoon.⁶ Checking the *Universal Lexicon*, we see that Almenräder is not entirely correct with his statement; two sorts of larger bassoons – transposing both a fourth and a fifth lower – and not one, are actually mentioned by Zedler (figure 3).

Fig. 3: Johann Heinrich Zedler, *Grosses vollständiges Universal-Lexicon aller Wissenschaften und Künste* 1731–1754

Furthermore, in his treatise about orchestration from 1843–44, Hector Berlioz mentions an instrument pitched a fifth *higher*, explaining that the “basson quinte” is stronger and has a less “touching” sound quality than the “Corno anglais”. He also suggests that small bassoons might be advantageously used to soften the harshness heard in military music bands, implying that this was not yet the case.⁷

⁶ Carl Almenräder, *Vollständige theoretisch praktische Fagottschule* (Mainz: Schott, 1843), 1. See also: Johann Heinrich Zedler, *Grosses vollständiges Universal-Lexicon aller Wissenschaften und Künste* 1731–1754, 94.

⁷ Hector Berlioz, *Grand Traité d’Instrumentation et d’Orchestration Modernes* (Paris: Schonenberger, n.d.[1844]), 133.

Museum and instrument collection catalogues use terms such as “quart-”, “quint-”, “sext-” and “octave-bassoon”, but also “Hochsext-”, “baritone”, “tenor-”, “alto-” “soprano-”, and “high-bassoon”; the name “bassonetti” is found in some scores. Furthermore, the existence of other bassoon-like instruments (“Russisches Fagott” and “Alto-Fagott” and a folded English horn) add to the over-all confusion.

For practical reasons in this project, we have decided to stay with the contemporary usage of “fagottino” as a *general name for small-scale bassoons*, but also to specifically refer to those *models pitched an octave higher than the full-size bassoon*. “Tenoroon” is reserved for reference to *models pitched a fourth or a fifth higher than the full-sized instrument*.

Repertoire classification

We have found various examples of specific scoring for “fagottino” and “tenoroon”, such as those shown in figures 4 and 5. The first, an excerpt from Porpora’s opera *Siface*, clearly lies well out-of-range for a full-scale bassoon from the eighteenth-century and is written in treble clef.⁸ The second, found in a four-part march, calls for a different instrument than that used in the bass line.⁹

Fig. 4: Nicola Antonio Porpora, *Siface*, Act III, Scena I (1730)

Fig. 5: Uri K. Hill, “Gov. Sullivan's march” (1807–08)

⁸ Nicola Antonio Porpora, *Siface*, Act III, Scena I (Rome 1730, fol. 268r). [Manuscript autograph in the Library of the Brussels Royal Conservatoire.]

⁹ Uri K. Hill, *Gov. Sullivan's march* (Publisher not indicated, United States, 1807–08, monograph). Retrieved from the Library of Congress, www.loc.gov/item/2015560592/, accessed on July 30, 2018. Probably composed for and performed at an official event.

Even though the actual range of the bassoon was always relatively large (up to three and a half octaves by the early nineteenth century), the highest register had its specific, technical challenges.¹⁰ Berlioz warned that the notes from b^{\flat} – e^{\flat} were ‘hazardous’ (fig. 6), and advised composers not to write above b^{\flat} .¹¹

Fig. 6: Hector Berlioz, *Grand Traité d'Instrumentation et d'Orchestration Modernes*

A key issue seems to be that composers generally may not have specified which size bassoon was intended to be used in their works. This would explain why some passages are out of the practical compass of a full-scale bassoon, or at least particularly awkward to execute in the keys written. Therefore, the logical solution would be for a player to choose the most appropriate-sized instrument, as suggested by Hubmann.

Following this lead, we can present several examples that would be most suitable on smaller, transposing instruments. In figure 7, an excerpt is displayed (one of many found in the opera *L'Isola disabitata* by Davide Perez), demonstrating the doubling of the viola line by the bassoons in alto clef.¹² The first part goes up to d^{\flat} , an unlikely possibility for a bassoon from this period:

¹⁰ Donna Agrell, ‘Repertoire for a Swedish Bassoon Virtuoso: Approaching early nineteenth-century works composed for Frans Preumayr with an original Grenser & Wiesner bassoon’, PhD dissertation (Leiden, 2015). URL: <https://openaccess.leidenuniv.nl/handle/1887/36960>. See reports about range and Frans Preumayr, 54–57; 97.

¹¹ Berlioz (1844), 128.

¹² Davide Perez, *L'Isola disabitata*, Palermo (1748). [Biblioteca del Conservatorio di musica S. Pietro a Majella (I-Nc): 30.4.5]

Fig. 7: Davide Perez, *L'Isola disabitata*, Palermo, 1748 (Overture, Andante molto, “Fagotti con le Viole”)

In another more famous instance, a bassoonist from the late eighteenth century would have struggled with high-register fingerings in Beethoven’s trio in an attempt to execute the following passage in an elegant and delicate manner equal to that of the flute (figure 8).¹³ If we also consider that the work was composed for an amateur, a tenoroon in G would be an obvious choice, ascending only up to f’ and using very simple fingering combinations.¹⁴

Fig. 8: Ludwig van Beethoven «Trio für Klavier, Flöte und Fagott in G-Dur», WoO 37, II. Adagio

¹³ Ludwig van Beethoven, “Trio für Klavier, Flöte und Fagott”, WoO 37 (ca. 1786–90). A live performance video of this movement may be seen at: www.historical-bassoon.ch, “A taste of Beethoven with tenoroon”.

¹⁴ Kopp (2012), 225.

We have established a methodical system to analyze bassoon repertoire, considering aspects of playability such as range, keys, technical and musical demands and contexts, and are using this tool to compile a list of suggested musical works for small-sized bassoons. The repertoire list will also include any new discoveries of scoring which specifies these instruments, and will be regularly updated on our website: www.historical-bassoon.ch.

An instrument catalogue

The other main goal of the project is to publish a catalogue of as many surviving small-sized bassoons built between 1700 and 1914 as possible. The catalogue also includes references of instruments taken from several historical documents, such as instrument advertisements and articles from period newspapers, maker's inventories, letters, and so forth.

The idea of making a catalogue as part of a research project might at first sound out-of-date in the twenty-first century. Which first-rate university would accept a catalogue as “research output” of a PhD topic? In the era of digitalized information and big-data where one can obtain museum catalogues, instrument pictures, inventories, and far more information than is humanly possible to process all in one click, the challenge of a modern Humanities researcher lies in the ability of transforming the sort of raw information a catalogue offers into more philosophical thought, invoking cultural and historical insights into specific time periods. One of the main challenges we faced when we started the fagottino project was that we were lacking the most basic information about the instruments we were preparing to study. The variety of terminology found in museums and archives, discussed above, challenge any interested person searching for basic information.

Even after exploring the first raw organology, proof of the historical value of those instruments was somehow undermined, or even missing. Thus, the next task was to prove that small-sized bassoons were not just anecdotes or toys, as well as to document their existence previous to the mid-twentieth century. The idea of creating a catalogue became a starting point, on the way to complete a too-often-forgotten chapter in the history of the bassoon. The ground was finally set, and after collecting ca. 100 entries of surviving fagottini and tenoroons in only the first year, we are ready for the instruments to tell their own story.

As a simple list of instruments, proven necessary in this case, is not a research task that by itself belongs to the twenty-first century; the small-sized bassoon catalogue also includes a large amount of various information about specific instruments. This includes several detailed photos of most of the documented instruments and in the case of the most emblematic, a database with up to 200 measurements, some with additional bore dimensions.

Those entries include key measurements taken externally and internally, tone-hole angles, lengths, and positions, bore diameters of the bassoon parts, as well as other details.

INSTRUMENT CATALOGUE DETAIL						
ID Nr.	MAKER	INSTRUMENT	PROVENANCE	DATE	CURRENT LOCATION	STATUS
FT1	GEROCK, Christopher	tenoroon	London	ca.1804–37	St. Petersburg, Muzei Muzikalniĥ Instrumentov Teatra, Muziki, i Kinematografii	Not examined
FT2	GRENSER, Augustin	4-key fagottino	Dresden	ca.1744–98	Copenhagen, Musikhistorisk Museum ig Carl Claudius' Samling	Not examined
FT3	GRENSER, Heinrich 1	5-key fagottino	Dresden	ca.1800	The Hague, Gemeentemuseum	Examined by 3rd parties
	GRENSER, Heinrich 2	5-key fagottino	Dresden	ca.1796–13	Frankfurt am Main, Historisches Museum	Not examined
	GRENSER, Heinrich 3	6-key fagottino	Dresden	ca.1806–13	Berlin, Musikinstrumenten Museum. Staatliches Institut für Musikforschung	Not examined
FT4	GRENSER, Heinrich & WIESNER, Samuel	6-key fagottino	Dresden	ca.1824	Stockholm, Scenkonstmuseet	Examined
	HECKEL, Wilhelm	18-key tenoroon	Biebrich	1907	Unknown	Historical catalogue reference
FT5	HIRSCHBRUNNER, Gebrüder	11-key tenoroon	Sumiswald	ca.1815–47	Bern, Klingende Sammlung	Not examined
FT6	JACOBY Fils. 1	5-key fagottino	Auch	ca.1785	Paris, Philharmonie de Paris	Examined
FT7	KRAUS, I. 1	4-key tenoroon	Germany	ca.1775	Paris, Philharmonie de Paris	Examined
	KRAUS, I. 2	3-key tenoroon	Germany	ca.1750–90	München, Musikinstrumentenmuseum in Münchner Stadtmuseum	Not examined
	KRAUS, I. 3	3-key tenoroon	Germany	ca.1750–90	Hamamatsu-city, Japan, Hamamatsu Museum of Musical Instruments, (formerly in	Not examined

Fig. 9: Screenshot of instrument catalogue on website

In our catalogue, detailed measurement data allows a profound comparison between maker's styles, underlining regional and historical differences in small-sized bassoons, but also analogous to larger, full-sized bassoons. From data already collected, the fagottino and tenoroon reveal themselves to be instruments with their own characteristics, going beyond being small-versions of the bassoon to also having their own features.

A good example of the kinds of features discovered in this study is the cylindrical shape of the bell. This appears in several instruments from different makers, and has proven to be a common feature in the construction of small-sized bassoons. A few examples of instruments of diverse nature and origin that present an almost-cylindrical bell, are: 13-key tenoroon, Frédéric-Guillaume Adler, Paris, ca. 1840; 13-key tenoroon, Frédéric-Guillaume Adler, Paris, ca.1840, or 9-key tenoroon, Dominique A. Porthaux, Paris, ca.1808, among others.¹⁵

The data of the bore is collected adapting the method described by Jan Bouterse in *Dutch Woodwind Instruments and their Makers*.¹⁶ Most of the measurements are collected using a caliper-rod tool, proven to be the most common method used by instrument makers for bore-measuring.

¹⁵ See data collected on our website www.historical-bassoon.ch.

¹⁶ Jan Bourtesse, *Dutch woodwind instruments and their makers, 1660-1760* (Utrecht: Koninklijke Vereniging voor Nederlandse Muziekgeschiedenis, 2005).

First remarks about the instruments

As the catalogue shows, fagottini and tenoroons were built by the most renowned woodwind makers of the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. Instruments were found to be built in many different regions, therefore it is not possible to conclude if there was one unique, important fagottino nucleus.

Among Parisian makers who built small-sized instruments we found: Martin Lot, Christophe Delusse, Dominique Porthaux, and Frédéric-Guillaume Adler, as well as others. The famous Savary family also made numerous instruments. Both the elder, Savary père, from whom a tenoroon is preserved in the Philharmonie of Paris, as well as his son, Jean Nicholas Savary Jeune, built several instruments. Figure 10 shows an extraordinary example by Savary Jeune made in 1827. The 14-key fagottino exhibits a particular key-work system, with a crossed-A^b key in the back of the butt joint and ivory reinforcement in several tone holes. This fagottino and other Savary tenoroons demonstrate outstanding craftsmanship, suggesting they were constructed for professional use.

Fig. 10: FT 25, detail of key work from *14-key fagottino*, Jean-Nicholas Savary Jeune, Paris, 1827

Even if the French musical center at that time was in Paris, fagottino makers were distributed in other French-speaking regions as well, such as in Tours (François-Xavier Proff), Auch (Jacoby Fils), and Strasburg, where the famous Bühner & Keller makers were located.

Figure 11 shows a 5-key fagottino stamped by Jacoby Fils in Auch, close to the Spanish border in the south of France. This late eighteenth-century fagottino is made of boxwood, instead of maple or fruit-tree wood; not a rare choice for small instruments, especially those from that period.

Fig. 11: FT17, 5-key fagottino, Jacoby Fils, Auch, ca.1785

In Brussels, G.A. Rottenburgh, and in Mechelen, Jean Arnold Tuerlinckx also built several small-sized instruments. Furthermore, many instruments have survived that were made in the London area and other English cities by makers such as: William Milhouse, Horwood & Astor, Charles Pace, Thomas Saxton, J. Collings, and John Blockley.

Thomas Cahusac made the tenoroon in G shown in figure 12. This instrument has an inscription with the date 1789 under the A^b key on the butt joint – a happy coincidence with the revolutionary events that changed Europe forever. It has the characteristically-shaped keys of English instruments from the period. The initials I.H. are inscribed beneath the keys, which stand for John Hale, a craftsman whose signature appears on several instruments from the time. Made by Thomas Cahusac, although as Waterhouse in the *New Langwill Index* points out, it is almost impossible to determine if instruments from the late eighteenth century were made by Thomas Cahusac Senior, active between 1738 and 98, or Thomas Cahusac Junior, who started working with his father in 1780 and continued until 1814.¹⁷

Fig. 12: FT11, 6-key tenoroon, Thomas Cahusac, London, 1789

¹⁷ William Waterhouse, *The New Langwill Index* (London: Tony Bingham 1993), 54–55.

Among makers from the Italian peninsula we find: Bonaccorsi from Barga, Castlas from Torino, and Cristofaro Custode and De Rosa from Naples, although the latter is not confirmed to be a maker but an instrument dealer.¹⁸

From German cities, several outstanding instruments from the eighteenth century have survived, including those made by Johann Christoph Denner from Nuremberg, Johann Heinrich Eichentopf from Leipzig, Heinrich Carl Tölcke from Braunschweig, Johann Leiberz from Koblenz, Augstin and Heinrich Grenser, from Dresden, as well the later union of Grenser & Wiesner, in the nineteenth century. Other makers of German origin are Schramme, Müller, Kuteruf, and I. Kraus.

In Butzbach, the Scherer factory was an important woodwind-making center in the eighteenth century. Johannes and Georg Heinrich Scherer built several fagottino, of which six have survived that are preserved in different museums. Figure 13 shows a 4-key Scherer fagottino in a very good state of preservation, currently in the Music Instrument Museum in Brussels. As discussed by Young, several craftsmen worked under the Scherer label, stamping their creations with their initials.¹⁹ The various Scherer fagottini found up to now share this characteristic, having different letters drawn in the wood, indicating how small bassoons were made not only by one maker, but several; a clear indication of the importance that small-sized bassoons had in the Scherer instrument-making workshop.

Fig. 13: FT29, 4-key fagottino, Johannes & Georg Scherer, Butzbach, ca.1764

¹⁸ Ibid, 334.f

¹⁹ Phillip T. Young, “The Scherers of Butzbach” in *The Galpin Society Journal*, Vol. 39 (Sep. 1986), 112–24.

By the turn of the nineteenth century, Viennese and nearby makers also built several instruments, such as those by Wolfgang Küss, Kaspar Tauber, Magvini, Johann Stehle, Franz Scholl, Franz Wussinger, and Johann Joseph Merklein, whose tenoroon is shown in figure 14. This 8-key tenoroon has the key-work system typical of bassoons made in Vienna in the nineteenth century, where the two wing-joint keys are uniquely-placed. On Merklein's instrument, as was common in bassoons from that region, the tone hole closer to the bocal well (C) is operated by the longer key, while the A-key is shorter and operated with the thumb pointing upwards. This is a completely different key placement than the those found on German, French, and English instruments, where the two keys are inverted.

Fig. 14: FT19, *8-key tenoroon*, I. Merklein, Vienna, ca. 1835

Moreover, Swiss makers such as Jeremias Schlegel or the Hirschbrunner family also built examples of fagottini and tenoroons.

Historical hints about fagottino and tenoroon

A close analysis of the instruments examined so far can also help determine crucial facts about the history of small-sized bassoon construction, such as what types were more common in different regions and time periods. Moreover, measurements taken are essential in order to determine facts about pitch. As previously stated, the small-sized bassoons are classified as fagottini and tenoroons; the first sounds one octave higher than the full-sized bassoon, and the latter normally pitched in G or F.

As it is not always possible to try original instruments, it is sometimes difficult to determine what their transposing pitches are. Here, measurements play a significant role. The comparison in Table 1 shows some the external lengths (or standing lengths) taken from 35 instruments: 1) the bottom of the butt joint to the top of the bell; 2) the bottom of the butt joint to the top of wing joint; 3) the total length in millimeters, derived by adding the two measurements. The instruments are chronologically-ordered and give important information about geographical trends in instrument-making and transposing pitch.

ID NR	INSTRUMENT, MAKER, PLACE, DATE	Length - butt to bell	Length - butt to wing	TOTAL external length
FT14	<i>3-key fagottino</i> , Johann C. Denner, Nuremberg ca.1700	636	447.7	1083.7
FT7	<i>3-key fagottino</i> , Anonymous, ca.1730–1780	646.5	473.5	1120
FT23	<i>4-key fagottino</i> , Godfridus A. Rottenburgh, Brussels, ca.1760	667	448	1115
FT28	<i>4-key fagottino</i> , Johannes & Georg Scherer, Butzbach, ca.1760	639	459	1098
FT29	<i>4-key fagottino</i> , Johannes & Georg Scherer, Butzbach, ca.1764	642	464	1106
FT20	<i>4-key fagottino</i> , Müller, Germany, ca.1770	647	467	1114
FT30	<i>5-key fagottino</i> , Johannes & Georg Scherer, ca.1760–78	641	460	1101
FT18	<i>4-key tenoroon</i> , I. Kraus, Germany, ca.1775	764	589	1353
FT9	<i>4-key tenoroon</i> , John Blockley, Leicestershire, ca.1780	830	637	1467
FT4	<i>4-key fagottino</i> , Anonymous, ca.1780	641	463	1104
FT32	<i>4-key fagottino</i> , Heinrich C. Tölke, Braunschweig, ca.1780	647		

FT13	<i>7-key fagottino</i> , Christophe Delusse, Paris, ca.1783	626	418.5	1044.5
FT17	<i>5-key fagottino</i> , Jacoby Fils, Auch, ca.1785	636	440	1076
FT11	<i>6-key tenoroon</i> , Thomas Cahusac, London, 1789	837	641	1478
FT33	<i>4-key fagottino</i> , Jean A. Tuerlinckx, Mechelen, ca.1795	644	466	1110
FT3	<i>4-key fagottino</i> , Anonymous, Austrian Empire, ca.1800	635	471	1106
FT12	<i>7-key fagottino</i> , Castlas, Turin, ca.1800	599	400 / 373	999 / 972
FT16	<i>5-key fagottino</i> , Heinrich Grenser, Dresden ca.1800	669.3	472.8	1142.1
FT22	<i>5-key tenoroon</i> , François-Xavier Proff, Tours, ca.1800	716	563	1279
FT21	<i>9-key tenoroon</i> , Dominique A. Porthaux, Paris, ca.1808	937	642	1579
FT24	<i>5-key tenoroon</i> , Savary pere, Paris, ca.1810	762	551	1313
FT6	<i>8-key tenoroon</i> , Anonymous, Austrian Empire, ca.1815	840	563	1403
FT8	<i>6-key tenoroon</i> , Georg Astor & Horwood, London, ca.1815	890	680	1570
FT10	<i>7-key fagottino</i> , Bonaccorsi, Barga, ca.1815	630.5	435.5	1062.9
FT31	<i>6-key tenoroon</i> , Kaspar Tauber, Vienna, ca.1815	875	586	1461
FT34	<i>5-key tenoroon</i> , Jean A. Tuerlinckx, Mechelen, ca.1820	977	681	1658
FT15	<i>6-key fagottino</i> , H. Grenser & S. Wiesner, Dresden, ca.1824	670	449.5	1119.5
FT25	<i>14-key fagottino</i> , Jean-Nicholas Savary de Jeune, Paris, 1827	645	425	1070
FT35	<i>0-key unfinished fagottino</i> , Joseph Dupré, Tournai, ca.1830	637.5	447	1084.5
FT1	<i>11-key tenoroon</i> , Frédéric-Guillaume Adler, Paris, ca.1835	940	662	1602
FT19	<i>8-key tenoroon</i> , I. Merklein, Vienna, ca.1835	952	663	1615
FT26	<i>12-key tenoroon</i> , Jean-Nicholas Savary de Jeune, Paris, ca.1838	982	660	1642
FT2	<i>13-key tenoroon</i> , Frédéric-Guillaume Adler, Paris, ca.1840	947	630	1577
FT27	<i>16-key tenoroon</i> , Jean-Nicholas Savary de Jeune, Paris, 1841	980	658.5	1638.5
FT5	<i>13-key tenoroon</i> , Anonymous“S”, Paris, ca.1860	948.5	631	1579.5

Table 1: Instrument external lengths

An analysis of this data defines, for instance, that the octave-higher fagottino (marked in grey) total lengths are between 1000 mm and 1142 mm, differentiating themselves from the tenoroons that can reach up to 1642 mm.

As the instruments shown in Table 1 follow a chronological order, it is also possible to trace their geographical patterns, indicating that most of the smaller octave instruments were built in German regions in the mid-1700s. Smaller tenoroons (pitched in G) appeared in central Europe from France to England, existing together with smaller sizes arriving in England at the turn of the nineteenth century. Larger tenoroons pitched in F generally started to be built relatively late in the first quarter of the nineteenth century and from Paris, they rapidly started to be in fashion from Vienna to London.

Conclusion

As the scope of this research project has proven to be more significant and larger than originally envisioned, future projects will hopefully be able to address many more open questions, with thorough investigations of makers, performers, repertoire, and historical practice, as well as instrument re-construction. The pilot project team meanwhile continues its compilation of the detailed documentation of surviving instruments, collecting measurements and other organological data, along with repertoire analysis and classification. The research outcomes will not only alter our perceptions about the instruments of the historical bassoon family, but ultimately offer new sounds and colours to the tonal palette of performers.